

The Psychological Role of the Father in Education of the Young Generation

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Abstract: This in the article young generation bring up and in it your father role, responsibility and task and duties issues is dedicated. Also this in the article a child upbringing this just Experience is simple instruction and knowledge summation not but own into religious and moral knowledge, ethics, psychology, pedagogy such as to the fields about knowledge too cover will receive complicated process the fact that emphasized. That's it because of this small research educators, pedagogues, psychologists and parents for important have.

Keywords: value, depression, parents, duty, communication, behavior, psychology, spiritual maturity, spiritual prosperity.

Your father opinion of the child psychological development and to the well-being significant effect shows. Parents of their children behavior, abilities and choices how perception reach and assessment their himself himself appreciation, trust and common spiritual to health long term effect to show can This article parents child psychology of reasoning wider including its influence self respect make, personality formation and emotional in order to put effect to learn directed. If parents of his child behavior or features constant respectively criticism if he does or belittle let's say this himself himself appreciate feeling to decrease take coming can Children this comments own into take and to himself relatively negative the imagination development can On the contrary, parents positive comments and confirmations of the child to himself has been respect to increase can Children their parents by confession done and if they feel supported, they have healthy himself himself understanding probability more will be Choices and decisions their parents by constant respectively judgment to be done or void to be done children autonomy feeling development for to fight can It's theirs strong and independent person formation ability effect to do can. Parents of life different aspects, for example, profession choice, relationship and personal to beliefs has been relationship and comments of the child personal values system and personality to form significant effect to show possible Parents constant criticism or judgment in children worry and of stress to increase help gives These are their feelings in order put and difficulties overcome ability effect to do can Parents by judgment done children their feelings open expression in reaching suffering and healthy emotional in order put skills in development to difficulties take coming can Your parents hard judgment under grew up children adulthood at the age of healthy relationships formation and save to stay with to fight because it is possible their himself himself to appreciate and emotional in order to be put effect to do can. Parents of judgment effect adulthood to his age until stretching it is possible worry disorders, depression and low self- esteem such as to problems

help gives In the family open and without judgment communication encourage to the children heard and to feel understood help gives constructive feedback positive strengthening with balancing of the child psychological development for supportive and educator environment to create can Own judgments of his child to psychology potential recognized the effect parents parenthood approach improve professional help for and guidance to ask can

CONCLUSION

In general, in the family your father to be of the child social skills in formation big importance occupation is enough Professor V. Karimova also owns this observations relying on confirmed by: Your father love the same for a girl until the important thing is that he is a parent relationships life during watching go in the future own marriage to the seat how in relation to be it is necessary to the question answer finds Mother behavior looking while marriage a friend with happy to live for a woman how to be need said of the question core it stings That's why for of the family for both a girl and a boy idol, parents of relations warm, sincere, humanistic to be big vital importance occupation is enough So, the child himself meaning, which one gender representative that understanding and vital of imagination in formation parenthood of relations whole to be big important have

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